

The Effect of Motivation and Work Environment on the Performance of Employees in the Division of Pt. Socfindo Dolok Still

Benhart Nainggolan

Sekolah Tinggi Ilmu Ekonomi Bina Karya

ABSTRACT: This research shows. (1) It can be seen that the amount of adjusted R square value is 0.743 or 74.3% This shows that the Work Motivation Variable (X1) and Work Environment Variable (X2) can explain the Employee Performance Variable (Y) of 74.3% , the remaining 25.7% (100% - 74.3%) is explained by other variables outside the research model. (2) The results of the t-test (partial) can be seen that the obtained t count is 4,750 with = 5%, t-table (5%; 34-2 = 32) the t-table value is 1,694. From the description it can be seen that t-count (4,750) > t-table (1.694), as well as the significance value of 0.00 <0.05, it can be concluded that the first hypothesis is accepted, meaning that the Work Motivation Variable (X1) has a significant effect on the Employee Performance Variable (Y). (3) The results of the t-test (partial) can be seen that the t count value is 5.915 with = 5%, t-table (5%; 34-2 = 32) the t table value is 1.694. From the description it can be seen that t count (5.915) > t-table (1.694), and the significance value of 0.00 <0.05, it can be concluded that the second hypothesis is accepted, meaning that the Work Environment Variable (X2) has a significant effect on the Employee Performance Variable (Y). (4) The results of the simultaneous test (F) can be seen that the value of F-count (48.721) > F-table (3.30), and a significance value of 0.000 <0.05, it can be concluded that the third hypothesis is accepted, meaning that the Work Motivation Variable (X1), Variable Work Environment (X2) has a significant effect simultaneously (simultaneously) on Employee Performance Variables (Y).

KEYWORDS: Work Motivation, Work Environment and Performance Variables

INTRODUCTION

In order to face the current era of globalization, it is often found several problems that cause many companies to fail, both caused by the inability to adapt to technological advances or caused by the poor work results of the existing human resources in the company, even though it must be acknowledged that the source Human resources are a very important factor that determines the success of a company.

According to Simanjuntak (2005) in Widodo (2015) Performance is the level of achievement of results on the implementation of certain tasks. Simanjuntak also defines individual performance as the level of achievement or results of a person's work from targets that must be carried out within a certain period of time. To be able to carry out their duties and functions as well as possible, good performance is needed so as to create good work results for the company. In improving employee performance, a company must have agency goals that will be more easily achieved, and vice versa if employee performance is low or not good.

According to Sunyoto (2013: 43) the work environment is everything that is around the worker and that can affect him in carrying out the assigned tasks. PT Socfin Indonesia is a company engaged in agribusiness & related industries. The company is the largest global processor and business for palm oil. In addition, this company is also one of the largest oil palm plantation owners and the largest biodiesel producer in the world. PT Socfin Indonesia routinely every year always conducts performance assessments carried out by the heads of fields in each division using the SMK (Performance Management System).

Based on the phenomenon that occurred to PT Socfin Indonesia Dolok Masihul, there were still very many mistakes from employees who did not comply with the standards set, this made the authors interested in studying more deeply about the performance of PT Socfin Indonesia Dolok Masihul into a thesis research. entitled **"INFLUENCE OF MOTIVATION AND WORK ENVIRONMENT ON THE PERFORMANCE OF DIVISION EMPLOYEES AT PT. SOCFINDO DOLOK STILL.**

The Effect of Motivation and Work Environment on the Performance of Employees in the Division of Pt. Socfindo Dolok Still

A. Problem Formulation

Based on the background of this research, to facilitate the analysis the writer formulates the problem as follows:

1. Does motivation affect the performance of employees of PT. Socfin Indonesia Dolok still?
2. Does the work environment affect the performance of employees of PT. Socfin Indonesia Dolok still?
3. Do motivation and work environment have a joint influence on the performance of employees of PT. Socfin Indonesia Dolok still?

B. Research purposes

As explained in the background of the problem, this study intends to examine the effect of work discipline and work motivation on employee performance. Specifically, the purpose of this research is to obtain information regarding:

- a. The influence of motivation on the performance of employees of PT. Socfin Indonesia Dolok Masihul
- b. The influence of the work environment on the performance of employees of PT. Socfin Indonesia Dolok Masihul
- c. The influence of motivation and work environment together on the performance of employees of PT. Socfin Indonesia Dolok Masihul

THEORETICAL BASIS

A. Employee Performance

A company organization was founded because it has certain goals that it wants and must achieve. In achieving its goals every organization is influenced by organizational behavior. One of the most common activities carried out in organizations is employee performance, namely how he does everything related to a job or role in the organization.

According to Campbell (in Armstrong, 2014: 31) "Performance as behavior and stated that it should be distinguished from the outcomes because they can be contaminated by systems factors." (Performance as behavior and it is determined that it should be distinguished from results because it can be contaminated by system factors)

Bastian (2010:2) states that performance is a description of the level of achievement of the implementation of an activity/program/policy in realizing the goals, objectives, mission and vision of the organization contained in the formulation of an organization's strategic scheme (strategic planning). So, performance is the willingness of a person or group of people to carry out activities or perfect them in accordance with their responsibilities with results as expected.

According to Armstrong and Baron in Wibowo (2011:25) performance is the result of work that has a strong relationship with the strategic goals of the organization, customer satisfaction and contributes to the economy. According to Kasmir (2016: 182), performance is the result of work and work behavior that has been achieved in completing the tasks and responsibilities given in a certain period. Increased individual performance (individual performance) will most likely also improve company performance (corporate performance) because the two have a close relationship. "Teacher performance is behavior or response that gives results that refer to what they do when he or she faces a task. The performance of the teaching staff concerns all the activities or behavior experienced by the teaching staff, the answers they make, to give results or goals. Sometimes the performance of the teaching staff is only in the form of responses, but usually gives results (Yamin and Maisah, 2010:87).

The definition of performance above generally highlights the actions taken by a person in his existence either as a member, employee, manager, or even the leader of a particular organization, company or work group. Therefore, the terms and concepts of performance adorn many studies and practices in the field of management, as one of the vital concepts that determine the movement and development of certain management.

B. Work Motivation

According to Hasibuan (2012: 141), motivation questions how to direct the power and potential of subordinates, so that they want to work together productively to achieve and realize the goals that have been determined. Motivation is a condition that moves employees to be able to achieve the goals of their motives. Motivation in everyday life is defined as the whole process of giving encouragement or stimulation to employees so that they are willing to work willingly without being forced. From the description above, it can be stated that motivation is an activity or a way to encourage turmoil in humans to want to behave, work optimally to meet predetermined needs or goals.

The Effect of Motivation and Work Environment on the Performance of Employees in the Division of Pt. Socfindo Dolok Still

C. Work Environment

According to Sunyoto (2013: 43) the work environment is everything that is around the worker and that can affect him in carrying out the tasks assigned. A good job will encourage the creation of employee productivity at work, so that employees will be able to be directed properly and encourage the creation of motivation.

The work environment is a pleasant work atmosphere, the level of authoritarian superiors at work, the level of sources of advice in groups, the opportunity to develop their talents, peace and the space or place where they work (Arianto, 2013 in Nitisemito, 1991). Meanwhile, according to other experts stated that the work environment is as a whole of tools and materials encountered, the surrounding environment in which a person works, his work methods, and work arrangements both as individuals and as a group (Amalia, 2018 in Sedamayanti, 2001). important thing to support the process of achieving company goals, the work environment itself consists of physical and non-physical attached to employees so that it cannot be separated from employee development efforts (Lidya T. Rumengan, Peggy, 2015). The work environment is the overall work facilities and infrastructure around employees who are doing work that can affect the implementation of work (Diah I. Suwondo, 2015 in Sutrisno, 2009).

RESEARCH METHOD

1. Location and Time of Research

a. Research sites

This research will be carried out at PT. Socfin Indonesia Dolok Masihul, Serdang Bedagai, North Sumatra.

b. Research time

This research will be carried out from February 2019 to August 2019

2. Data Collection Techniques

Data collection methods used in this study are:

a. Interview

The technique of collecting data by interview is a technique of collecting data by using oral questions to research subjects. This is done to get an overview of the problems that usually occur due to special causes that cannot be explained by questionnaires.

b. Questionnaire

The technique of collecting data with a questionnaire is a data collection technique by providing a list of questions to respondents, with the hope that respondents will respond to questions in the questionnaire. In this questionnaire, a closed question model will be used, namely the form of questions that have been accompanied by previous alternative answers, so that respondents can choose one of the alternative answers.

In the measurement, each respondent is asked for his opinion on a statement, with a rating scale from 1 to 5. Positive responses (maximum) are given the largest value (5) and negative responses (minimum) are given the smallest value (1).

DISCUSSION

Descriptive Analysis of Research Variables

1. Work Motivation Variable (X1)

Based on Appendix 2, it is known the number and percentage of respondents' answers regarding Work Motivation Variables as presented in Table 1 below:

Table 1. Description of Respondents' Answer Score Regarding Work Motivation Variables (X1)

Statement	Answer				
	SS	S	KS	TS	STS
1. I agree if employees are given motivation regarding the need for work performance.	6 orang (17,6%)	21 orang (61,8%)	7 orang (20,6%)	-	-
2. The leader provides direction to improve the performance of all employees.	6 orang (17,6%)	21 orang (61,8%)	7 orang (20,6%)	-	-

The Effect of Motivation and Work Environment on the Performance of Employees in the Division of Pt. Socfindo Dolok Still

3. I agree if the company gives encouragement to employees to be more familiar with each other for the smooth running of the company.	16 orang (47,1%)	12 orang (35,3%)	4 orang (11,8%)	2 orang (5,9%)	-
4. I am always advised to care more about others in order to motivate myself.	7 orang (20,6%)	24 orang (70,6%)	3 orang (8,8%)	-	-

Table 1 shows that the average respondent's answer is on the agree and strongly agree scale with the average answer value of 4.07 (high). This shows that from the 4 measurement indicators of Work Motivation Variable (X1) it can be concluded that the average Work Motivation Variable (X1) is in the high category.

2. Work Environment Variable (X2)

Based on Appendix 2, it is known the number and percentage of respondents' answers regarding Work Environment Variables as presented in Table 2 below:

Table 2. Description of Respondents' Answer Scores Regarding Work Environment Variables

Statement	Answer				
	SS	S	KS	TS	STS
1. I feel comfortable working in the factory because the building is big and strong and the company always pays more attention to it	8 orang (23,5%)	20 orang (58,8%)	6 orang (17,6%)	-	-
2. I was given work equipment such as K3 equipment.	5 orang (14,7%)	21 orang (61,8%)	8 orang (23,5%)	-	-
3. I have the facilities provided by the company as its responsibility.	10 orang (29,4%)	9 orang (26,5%)	13 orang (38,2%)	2 orang (5,9%)	-

Table 2 agrees with the average answer value of 3.89 (high). This shows that from the 4 measurement indicators of Work Environment Variables (X2), it can be concluded that the average score of Work Environment Variables is in the high category.

3. Employee Performance Variable (Y)

Based on Appendix 2, it is known the number and percentage of respondents' answers regarding Employee Performance Variables (Y) as presented in Table 3 below:

Table 3. Description of Respondents' Answer Score Regarding Employee Performance Variables (Y)

Statement	Answer				
	SS	S	KS	TS	STS
1. I am able to carry out the work tasks of the company well and according to the target	9 orang (26,5%)	15 orang (44,1%)	9 orang (26,5%)	1 orang (2,9%)	-
2. The quality of my work is always considered good in the company in order to further improve performance.	7 orang (20,6%)	24 orang (70,6%)	3 orang (8,8%)	-	-
3. I am always on time and meet targets when doing work assignments and responsibilities	5 orang (14,7%)	21 orang (61,8%)	8 orang (23,5%)	-	-
4. All work given by superiors can be done effectively.	10 orang (29,4%)	9 orang (26,5%)	13 orang (38,2%)	2 orang (5,9%)	-

The Effect of Motivation and Work Environment on the Performance of Employees in the Division of Pt. Socfindo Dolok Still

Table 3 shows that the average respondent's answers are on the agree and strongly agree scale with the average answer value of 3.94 (high). This shows that from the 4 measurement indicators of the Employee Performance Variable (Y) it can be concluded that the average score of the Employee Performance Variable is in the high category.

1. Reliability Test

Reliability is an index that shows the extent to which a measuring instrument can be trusted or reliable. According to Sugiyono (2013) a factor is declared reliable if the Cronbach Alpha is greater than 0.6. Based on the results of data processing using SPSS 23 for windows, the following results were obtained:

Table 4 Reliability Test Results

Variable	<i>Cronbach Alpha</i>	Constant	Reliability
Variable X1	0,781	0,6	Reliabel
Variable X2	0,754	0,6	Reliabel
Y . variable	0,739	0,6	Reliabel

Based on the reliability test using Cronbach Alpha, all research variables are reliable/reliable because Cronbach Alpha is greater than 0.6, so the results of this study indicate that the measurement tool in this study has met the reliability test (reliable and can be used as a measuring instrument).

Classic assumption test

The testing of classical assumptions with the SPSS 23 for windows program carried out in this study includes:

1. Normality Test

Normality test aims to test whether in the regression model, the confounding or residual variables have a normal distribution (Ghozali, 2016). Testing the normality of the data can be done using two methods, graphs and statistics. The normality test of the graph method uses a normal probability plot, while the statistical method normality test uses the one sample Kolmogorov Smirnov Test. The test results using SPSS 23 for windows are as follows:

Table 5. One Sample Kolmogorov Smirnov Test

One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test

		Unstandardized Residual	
N		34	
Normal Parameters ^{a,b}	Mean	,0000000	
	Std. Deviation	,92154999	
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	,088	
	Positive	,088	
	Negative	-,068	
Test Statistic		,088	
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		,200 ^{c,d}	
Monte Carlo Sig. (2-tailed)	Sig.	,971 ^e	
	99% Confidence Interval	Lower Bound	,896
		Upper Bound	1,000

a. Test distribution is Normal.

b. Calculated from data.

c. Lilliefors Significance Correction.

d. This is a lower bound of the true significance.

e. Based on 34 sampled tables with starting seed 2000000.

The Effect of Motivation and Work Environment on the Performance of Employees in the Division of Pt. Socfindo Dolok Still

From the output in table 5, it can be seen that the significance value (Monte Carlo Sig. Lower Bound) of all variables is 0.896. If the significance is more than 0.05, then the residual value is normal, so it can be concluded that all variables are normally distributed.

Data that is normally distributed will form a straight diagonal line and plotting the residual data will be compared with a diagonal line, if the distribution of residual data is normal, the line that describes the actual data will follow the diagonal line (Ghozali, 2016).

2. Multicollinearity Test

The multicollinearity test aims to determine whether there is a correlation between the independent variables in the regression model. The multicollinearity test in this study is seen from the tolerance value or variance inflation factor (VIF). The calculation of the tolerance value or VIF with the SPSS 23 for windows program can be seen in Table 6 below:

Table 6 Multicollinearity Test Results Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		Collinearity Statistics		
		B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.	Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	-,160	1,631		-,098	,923		
	Motivasi_X1	,447	,094	,460	4,750	,000	,829	1,206
	Lingkungan_Kerja_X2	,554	,094	,573	5,915	,000	,829	1,206

a. Dependent Variable: Performance_Employee_Y

Based on table 6, it can be seen that the tolerance value of Work Motivation Variable (X1) is 0.829 Work Environment Variable (X2) is 0.829, where all of them are greater than 0.10 while the VIF value of Work Motivation Variable (X1) is 1.206, Environmental Variable Work (X2) is 1.206, all of which are smaller than 10. Based on the results of the above calculations, it can be seen that the tolerance value of all independent variables is greater than 0.10 and the VIF value of all independent variables is also smaller than 10 so that there is no correlation symptom. on the independent variable. So it can be concluded that there is no symptom of multicollinearity between independent variables in the regression model.

3. Heteroscedasticity Test

The heteroscedasticity test aims to test whether from the regression model there is an inequality of variance from the residuals of one observation to another observation. A good regression model is one with homoscedasticity or no heteroscedasticity. One way to detect the presence or absence of heteroscedasticity is by using a scatterplot. Based on the results of data processing, the heteroscedasticity test in this study is shown in Figure 4.2 below:

Multiple Linear Regression Test

Multiple linear regression testing explains the role of Work Motivation Variable (X1), Work Environment Variable (X2) on Employee Performance Variable (Y). Data analysis in this study used multiple linear regression analysis using SPSS 23 for windows. The analysis of each variable is described in the following description:

Table 7. Multiple Linear Regression Results Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		Collinearity Statistics		
		B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.	Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	-,160	1,631		-,098	,923		
	Motivasi_X1	,447	,094	,460	4,750	,000	,829	1,206
	Lingkungan_Kerja_X2	,554	,094	,573	5,915	,000	,829	1,206

a. Dependent Variable: Performance_Employee_Y

The Effect of Motivation and Work Environment on the Performance of Employees in the Division of Pt. Socfindo Dolok Still

Based on these results, the multiple linear regression equation has the formulation: $Y = a + b_1X_1 + b_2X_2 + \dots$, so that the equation is obtained: $Y = -0.160 + 0.447X_1 + 0.554X_2$

The description of the multiple linear regression equation above is as follows:

1. The constant value (a) of -0.160 indicates the magnitude of the Employee Performance Variable (Y) if the Work Motivation Variable (X1), Work Environment variable (X2) is equal to zero.
2. The regression coefficient value of Work Motivation Variable (X1) (b1) of (0.447) indicates the magnitude of the role of Work Motivation Variable (X1) on Employee Performance Variable (Y) with the assumption that Work Environment Variable (X2) is constant. This means that if the work motivation variable (X1) increases by 1 unit value, it is predicted that the Employee Performance Variable (Y) will increase by (0.447) unit value assuming the Work Environment Variable (X2) is constant.
3. The value of the regression coefficient of the Work Environment Variable (X2) (b2) of (0.554) indicates the magnitude of the role of the Work Environment Variable (X2) on the Employee Performance Variable (Y) with the assumption that the Work Motivation Variable (X1) is constant. This means that if the Work Environment Variable (X2) factor increases by 1 unit value, it is predicted that the Employee Performance Variable (Y) will increase by (0.554) unit value assuming the Work Motivation Variable (X1) is constant.

Coefficient of Determination (R²)

The coefficient of determination is used to see how much the independent variable contributes to the dependent variable. In other words, the value of the determinant coefficient is used to measure the contribution of the studied variables X and Y as the dependent variables.

The greater the value of the coefficient of determination, the better the ability of variable X to explain variable Y. If the determination (R²) is greater (closer to 1), it can be said that the influence of variable X is large on variable Y. The formula for the coefficient of determination is as follows:

This shows that the model used is getting stronger to explain the effect of variable X on variable Y. On the other hand, if the determination (R²) is getting smaller (close to zero), it can be said that the effect of variable X on variable Y is getting smaller. This shows that the model used is not strong enough to explain the effect of variable X on variable Y.

The value used to see the coefficient of determination in this study is in the adjusted R square column. This is because the adjusted R square value is not susceptible to the addition of independent variables. The value of the coefficient of determination can be seen in Table 8 below:

Table 8. Coefficient of Determination

Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted Square	R Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	,871 ^a	,759	,743	,951	1,685

a. Predictors: (Constant), Motivation_X1, Work Environment_X2

b. Dependent Variable: Performance_Employee_Y

Based on table 8, it can be seen that the adjusted R square value is 0.743 or 74.3%. This shows that the Work Motivation Variable (X1) and Work Environment Variable (X2) can explain the Employee Performance Variable (Y) of 74.3%, the rest is 25.7% (100% - 74.3%) is explained by other variables outside the research model.

Hypothesis testing

1. t test (Partial)

The t statistic test is also known as the individual significance test. This test shows how far the influence of the independent variable partially on the dependent variable.

In this study, partial hypothesis testing was carried out on each independent variable as shown in Table 9 below:

The Effect of Motivation and Work Environment on the Performance of Employees in the Division of Pt. Socfindo Dolok Still

**Table 9. Partial Test (t)
Coefficients^a**

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	-,160	1,631		-,098	,923		
	Motivasi_X1	,447	,094	,460	4,750	,000	,829	1,206
	Lingkungan_Kerja_X2	,554	,094	,573	5,915	,000	,829	1,206

a. Dependent Variable: Performance_Employee_Y

a. Hypothesis Testing the Effect of Work Motivation Variable (X1) on Employee Performance variable (Y)

The form of hypothesis testing based on statistics and curves can be described as follows:

Decision Making Criteria:

- 1) Accept H0 If $t_{count} < t_{table}$ or $-t_{count} > -t_{table}$ or Sig value. > 0.05
- 2) Reject H0 If $t_{count} > t_{table}$ or $-t_{count} < -t_{table}$ or Sig. < 0.05

From table 4.11, the t_{count} value is 4.750. With $\alpha = 5\%$, t_{table} (5%; 34-2 = 32) the t_{table} value is 1.694. From the description it can be seen that t_{count} (4.750) $>$ t_{table} (1.694), as well as the significance of $0.00 < 0.05$, it can be concluded that the first hypothesis is accepted, meaning that the Work Motivation Variable (X1) has a significant effect on the Employee Performance Variable (Y). This research is in accordance with previous research, namely Abigail Christykawuri Indyta Budiman (2018) The Effect of Labor Social Security on Employee Motivation and Performance (Study on Permanent Employees of Kebon Agung Sugar Factory, Malang). Faculty of Administrative Sciences Universitas Brawijaya Malang

b. Hypothesis Testing the Effect of Work Environment Variables (X2) on Employee Performance Variables (Y), the form of hypothesis testing based on statistics and curves can be described as follows:

Decision Making Criteria:

- 1) Accept, If $t_{count} > t_{table}$ or $-t_{count} > -t_{table}$ or Sig value. < 0.05
- 2) Reject, If $t_{count} < t_{table}$ or $-t_{count} < -t_{table}$ or Sig. > 0.05

From table 4.11, the t_{count} value is 5.915. With $\alpha = 5\%$, t_{table} (5%; 34-2 = 32) the t_{table} value is 1.694. From the description it can be seen that t_{count} (5.915) $>$ t_{table} (1.694), and the significance value is $0.00 < 0.05$, it can be concluded that the second hypothesis is accepted, meaning that the Work Environment Variable (X2) has a significant effect on the Employee Performance Variable (Y). This research is in accordance with previous research, namely Abigail Christykawuri Indyta Budiman (2018) The Effect of Labor Social Security on Employee Motivation and Performance (Study on Permanent Employees of Kebon Agung Sugar Factory, Malang). Faculty of Administrative Sciences Universitas Brawijaya Malang

2. Test F (Simultaneous)

This test basically shows whether all the independent variables included in this model have a joint effect on the dependent variable. The results of the F test can be seen in the following table 10:

Table 10. Simultaneous Test Results (F)

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	88,092	2	44,046	48,721	,000 ^b
	Residual	28,025	31	,904		
	Total	116,118	33			

a. Dependent Variable: Performance_Employee_Y

b. Predictors: (Constant), Environment_Work_X2, Motivation_X1

Decision Making Criteria:

The Effect of Motivation and Work Environment on the Performance of Employees in the Division of Pt. Socfindo Dolok Still

- a) If the calculated F value $> F$ table or Sig. < 0.05 then H_a is accepted and H_0 is rejected.
- b) If the calculated F value $< F$ table or Sig. > 0.05 then H_a is rejected and H_0 is accepted.

From table 4.12, the Fcount value is 48.721 With = 5%, dk numerator: 3, dk denominator: 34-2-1 (5%; 2; 31) obtained Ftable value of 3.30 From the description it can be seen that Fcount (48.721) $>$ Ftable (3.30), and a significance value of 0.000 $<$ 0.05, it can be concluded that the third hypothesis is accepted, meaning that the Work Motivation Variable (X1), Work Environment Variable (X2) have a significant effect simultaneously (simultaneously) on Employee Performance Variable (Y). This research is in accordance with previous research, namely Erma Oktaria (2018) The Effect of Salary, Incentives, and Social Security on Employee Work Motivation in an Islamic Economic Perspective (Study at Pt Sarhif Brother North Lampung). Faculty of Economics and Islamic Business, Raden Intan State Islamic University, Lampung.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of research and discussion in the previous chapter, it can be concluded as follows:

1. Testing the first hypothesis, with partial test analysis, the results of tcount are 4.750. With = 5%, ttable (5%; 34-2 = 32) the ttable value is 1.694. From the description it can be seen that tcount (4.750) $>$ ttable (1.694), as well as the significance value of 0.00 $<$ 0.05, it can be concluded that the first hypothesis is accepted, meaning that the Work Motivation Variable (X1) has a significant effect on the Employee Performance Variable (Y)
2. Testing the second hypothesis, with partial test analysis, the result is that the tcount value is 5.915 With = 5%, ttable (5%; 34-2 = 32) the ttable value is 1.694. t table (1.694), and the significance value of 0.00 $<$ 0.05, it can be concluded that the second hypothesis is accepted, meaning that the Work Environment Variable (X2) has a significant effect on the Employee Performance Variable (Y).
3. Testing the third hypothesis, with simultaneous analysis, the results obtained that Fcount (48.721) $>$ Ftable (3.30), and a significance value of 0.000 $<$ 0.05, it can be concluded that the third hypothesis is accepted, meaning that the Work Motivation Variable (X1), Environmental Variable Work (X2) has a significant effect simultaneously (simultaneously) on Employee Performance Variables (Y).

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- 1) Abigail Christykawuri Indyta Budiman. 2018. The Effect of Labor Social Security on Employee Motivation and Performance. Faculty of Administrative Sciences, Universitas Brawijaya, Malang.
- 2) Ahmad Tohardi. 2012. Practical Understanding of Human Resource Management, Tanjung Pura University. Mandar Maju, Bandung.
- 3) Anwar King Mangkunegara. 2009. Human Resource Management. PT. Rosdakarya Youth, Bandung.
- 4) Augusty, Ferdinand. 2009. Management Research Methods: Research Guidelines for Thesis, Thesis and Accompanied by Management Science. Diponegoro University, Semarang.
- 5) Alex S. Nitisemito. 2010. Personnel management Human Resource Management. Third Edition, Jakarta.
- 6) Erma Oktaria. 2018. Effect of Salary, Incentives, and Social Security on Employee Work Motivation in Islamic Economic Perspective. Faculty of Economics and Islamic Business, Raden Intan State Islamic University, Lampung.
- 7) E, Sutrisno . 2012. Indonesian Manpower Management, edition 2. PT. Earth Literature. Jakarta.
- 8) Ghozali, Imam. 2016. Application of Multivariate Analysis With SPSS Program, Diponegoro University Publishing Agency, Vol.100-125. Semarang.
- 9) Gibson, Ivancevich, Donnelly. 2010. Organization, Behavior, Structure, Process. Character Building. Jakarta.
- 10) Hani, T. Handoko. 2014. Personnel Management and Human Resources. BPFE-Yogyakarta. Yogyakarta.
- 11) Hasibuan, Malayu S. P. 2013. Human Resource Management, Revised Edition: Bumi Aksara. Jakarta.
- 12) Muhammad Zahari. 2014. The Effect of Work Environment on Employee Productivity of Aro Wood Business Unit Factory. PT. Nusantara VI Plantation. Jambi.
- 13) Prijodarminto, S. 2013. Discipline Tips Towards Success. PT Pradnya Paramita. Jakarta.
- 14) Sunyoto. 2013. Human Resource Management. Bandung: Faithful Library
- 15) Veithzal Rivai. 2014. Human Resource Management for Companies, 6th Edition, PT. Raja Grafindo Persada, Depok, 16956.